

RESEARCH ARTICLE

Transformative social innovation and rural collaborative workspace assemblages as a means of prefiguring community economies

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Abstract

Background

Collaborative Workspaces are rapidly growing and evolving across the world. Traditionally understood as an urban phenomenon, most research understands them as either 'entrepreneurial-led', as profit-driven and commercial spaces such as business incubators and accelerators, or 'community-led' as being bottom-up, not-for-profit ventures aimed at catering for the needs of their community. Recent years however have seen their diffusion beyond large urban agglomerations to small towns and villages, with their functions assumed to be more community-orientated. At the same time, social innovation, or social innovation processes have been gaining prominence in academia, policy, and practice, as they address societal problems and hold potential for new forms of social relations. This paper attempts to provide a novel framework towards understanding the transformative potential of rural collaborative workspaces, as they engage in processes of social innovation, by drawing from diverse and community economies literature and assemblage thinking.

Methods

The paper uses international case study comparison between rural Austria and Greece (One case from each country). Methods applied were: semi-structured interviews (N=28), participant observation and focus groups (2).

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Results

Community-led rural collaborative workspaces hold transformative potential from i) their ability to assist rural actors with their capacities and realizing their desires and ii) changing individual subjectivities towards collective. Through changing social relations in praxis and perceptions, we examine how social innovation processes through collaborative workspaces can be understood as a means of opening new economic subjectivities towards creating community economies as their transformative potential.

Conclusions

Although rural collaborative workspaces hold potential for societal transformation, they require further institutionalization and support to move beyond the interstitial and symbiotic stages of transformation.

Plain language summary

This article aims to understand how collaborative workspaces, also known as hubs, have the potential to transition away from capitalism, by valuing other practices that hold greater social and environmental considerations.

Keywords

Collaborative Workspaces, Social Innovation, Diverse Economies, Post Capitalism, Assemblage, Rural

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Introduction

Collaborative workspaces (hereafter CWS) have emerged initially in urban areas since the mid-2000s. Coworking spaces, creative hubs, hackerspaces, fab labs etc host nowadays more than 5 million coworkers worldwide (ergonomictrends.com). Although primarily an urban phenomenon, CWS have also started to spread in medium and small cities in the last few years, away from urban agglomerations (Avdikos & Merkel, 2020). Recent research suggests that 66% of CWS are located in urban regions, while the rest (34%) are in intermediate or rural regions (Marmo & Avdikos, 2024). CWS usually provide workspaces to freelancers, paid employees, digital nomads and remote workers in general, but also, they facilitate professional encounters and networking possibilities between different people and they can also act as mediums for cultural exchanges. Especially, CWS in small cities and towns can play the role of a socio-cultural center where locals can engage through new participatory modes in different kinds of projects that benefit their localities and that can eventually end up in social innovation (hereafter SI) processes and projects. The paper aims in unpacking the role of CWS as initiators and facilitators of SI processes in rural areas, looking at two community led CWS in Western Greece and Upper Austria.

According to Moulart *et al.* (2017) SI is i) a way of understanding a wide range of activities and practices oriented to addressing and *providing solutions to specific social problems* or meeting human needs. Moreover, SI ii) involves *changing relations* through the adoption of new social practices, institutional arrangements and/or forms of participation. This means that SI does not separate means from ends, but treats needs and problems as inherent in social relations. However, the effects of SI extend beyond the immediate meeting of needs. SI seems to improve long term opportunities for individuals and communities, through producing more efficient, effective and sustainable means for society to deal with its challenges, and that iii) can have a deeper *transformative impact* over communities and society.

Through the analysis of qualitative data, mainly through interviews and participant observation, we delve into the multiple sets of relations found in these two rural CWS and attempt to unpack the ways these arrangements cover local needs and at the same time they foster new social relations. Moreover, we engage with the literature in unpacking the ways CWS can also cause a transformative effect on social relations towards a post growth/post-capitalist society, challenging the ways local institutions work. To do so, a novel theoretical framework, consisting of Diverse and Community Economies and Assemblage Thinking will be elaborated upon.

Social innovation, assemblages and diverse economies: a literature review

The use of SI over the last 30 years has increased almost exponentially (Van der Have & Rubalcaba, 2016). Within academia the term's meaning varies across fields such as

innovation studies, management studies, sustainable and territorial development (Howaldt *et al.*, 2014). This wide array of understandings is said to both be of help (Moulart & MacCallum, 2019) and hinderance (Bock, 2012) to understanding the 'fuzzy' concept that is SI (ibid.). While not providing an exhaustive literature review of SI, this section will serve to unravel SI, while positioning the paper within the literature and allowing for a reconceptualization of the concept through Diverse and Community Economies (Gibson-Graham, 2008).

SI seems a 'contested' concept (Ayob *et al.*, 2016; Marques *et al.*, 2018). On the one hand 'social' innovation can be understood as social entrepreneurship whereby social entrepreneurs come up with innovative ideas to address society's most pressing challenges, while the other approach is more understood through collective action and the social and solidarity economy. We want to highlight the capitalocentric nature (Gibson-Graham, 2008) of the entrepreneurial understandings of SI, and aim to demonstrate how SI processes work beyond an organization, or individual entrepreneur. While not reducing the role they can have in these processes, we argue that SI is also not reducible to one actor, but it operates as a SI assemblage, as a whole of different actors that have a collective desire in addressing social problems.

Within the capitalocentric strand, SI is understood as a technocratic, entrepreneurial/market driven complement to the neoliberal state (e.g. Mulgan, 2006; Murray *et al.*, 2010). Much of the focus is on individual entrepreneurship and mainstream innovation approaches to 'solving' society's most pressing problems. Here, SI is understood as '*an idea of a need that isn't being met, coupled with an idea of how it could be met*' (Mulgan, 2006: 149) or more specifically "*new ideas (products, services and models) that simultaneously meet social needs and create new social relationships or collaborations. In other words, they are innovations that are both good for society and enhance society's capacity to act.*" (Murray *et al.*, 2010: 3). Such understandings promote a capitalocentric worldview, whereby civil society is viewed as an untapped source of innovative capacity that can be harnessed towards creating new markets and economic value. Such understandings have also pierced policy documents, with SI seen allowing governments to 'do more with less' (BEPA, 2014), increasing growth and competition while addressing society's most pressing problems (Fougère *et al.*, 2017).

Several scholars critique this capitalocentric discourse, generally as it proliferates both neoliberal governance and subject production (Bragaglia, 2021; Fougère *et al.*, 2017; Jessop *et al.*, 2013; Swyngedouw, 2005). In these interpretations, SI is understood as quick-fix solutions to social problems through the creation of active economical and entrepreneurial subjects for a capitalist economy (Arampatzi, 2022; Fougère *et al.*, 2017; Jessop *et al.*, 2013), while shifting social and environmental costs from the state to citizens (Fougère *et al.*, 2017; Swyngedouw, 2005).

Moving to the more critical strand of the literature, it has been developed over the last 30 years by Frank Moulaert and colleagues (e.g. [Moulaert et al., 2010](#); [Moulaert et al., 2013](#)), who developed SI as a concept vis-à-vis neoliberal practices and policies, originally understood as an alternative model of local development ([Moulaert et al., 2005](#)). With its roots in new social movements ([Godin, 2012](#); [Martinelli, 2010](#)), SI is understood not as an organizational form, but as ethical spatial projects, by changing social relations towards meeting human needs and not as a gap in the market to be addressed. [Moulaert & Mehmood \(2020: 17\)](#), portray how many SI's are rooted in socio-ecological movements, as consequences of increasing privatization, climate crisis and increasing social inequalities. Examples include the new-municipalist movements (e.g. in Madrid and Barcelona), the creation of new urban and rural commons, agroecological initiatives, local development experiments aiming to move past the market-based economy etc.

Thus, SI is broadly understood as *innovation in social relations by meeting human needs* ([Moulaert et al., 2013](#)). SI is understood as both a practice (collective satisfaction of human needs) and a process (changes in social relations, collective empowerment) ([Moulaert & Mehmood, 2020](#)). Part of our contribution is through understanding the underlying processes that lead to collective action, SI can be understood as a means of opening new economic subjectivities and post-capitalist possibilities ([Gibson-Graham, 2008](#); [Wright, 2010](#)) which we would like to conceptualize as the transformative potential of SI, building through Assemblage thinking, as the analytical tool.

Transformative SI

Despite the split in SI literature, there is a nascent literature regarding SI and societal transformation, that transcends the binary ([Moulaert & MacCallum, 2019](#)). An important contribution to its theory has been that of the EU funded TRANSIT project to develop a theory on transformative social innovation (e.g. [Avelino et al., 2019](#); [Haxeltine et al., 2016](#); [Pel et al., 2020](#)). Here, transformative SI is understood as a “*process, through which social innovations challenge, alter and/or replace established (and/or dominant) institutions in the social-material context*” ([Haxeltine et al., 2016: 19](#)). The theoretical framework of the project comes from sustainability transitions thinking and conceptualizes transformative SI through the Multi-Level Perspective framework (MLP) ([Geels, 2004](#)), whereby SI's need to adapt to dominant rule sets in society and adapt to institutional logics (such as state regulations or collaborating with institutions) to become institutionalized and have a transformative impact in society ([Pel et al., 2020](#)). Despite the value however, there are several conceptual limitations on this approach, that are generally existent in most transitions' literature. Firstly, there is a lack of critique regarding capitalism ([Chatterton, 2016](#); [Törnberg, 2021](#)) and secondly the MLP privileges structure and hierarchy, reproducing the very power relations responsible for the need for social change to take place ([Gillard et al., 2016](#)).

In contrast, coming from an anti-essentialist and relational ontology inspired by Deleuze and Guattari and Gibson-Graham, we aim to overcome such limitations. [Gibson-Graham & Roelvink \(2009\)](#) highlight how a re-reading of the three dimensions of SI (addressing social needs (through the inclusion of marginalized groups into society), changing social relations and collective empowerment/socio-political transformation) through Diverse and Community Economies (hereafter DCE) can enrich SI theory. Through a re-conceptualization of the economy as a diverse space of ethical and political action “what is usually regarded as ‘the economy’ —wage labor, market exchange of commodities, and capitalist enterprise” ([Gibson-Graham, 2008: 69](#)), becomes “just one particular set of economic relations situated in a vast sea of economic activity” ([Gibson-Graham, 2008: 70](#)). Rather than a dominant capitalist economy, [Gibson-Graham \(2008\)](#) ask us to read for difference over dominance, and understand the diversity of economic activity at play, such as “non-market gifts, volunteer work, commons, cooperative forms of production, criminal economies and much more” ([Smith, 2020: 596](#)).

[Gibson-Graham & Roelvink \(2009\)](#) use the example of Argentina post-2008 financial crisis, to demonstrate how SI processes can encourage alternative modes of development, with interstitial transformations emerging from the cracks of a crisis stemming from the capitalist economy – “*the unemployed started to build community economies by engaging in barter and using alternative currencies, providing neighbourhood-based social services and schooling, and taking over factories and running them cooperatively*” (P. 32). What is key to these intentional/community economies was the processes that preceded them – “*To transform themselves into community economic subjects, they created a cooperative radio station; they went to the World Social Forum in Porto Alegre to see themselves reflected in others who were also engaged in projects of self-determination.*” (p. 32). It is this process of subject formation for the community economy and opening up of economic diversity in the economy we would like to stress as the desired transformation for post-capitalism, without stressing an end product, but process, struggle and deliberation ([Gibson-Graham & Roelvink, 2009](#)).

Furthermore, in *Real Utopias* [Olin Wright \(2010\)](#) develops a robust theoretical framework for post-capitalist transformation through envisaging real utopias - “*proposals for pragmatically improving our institutions. Instead of indulging in utopian dreams we must accommodate to practical realities.*” (p. 4). Wright identifies three main ‘pathways’ for social transformation: radical ‘ruptural’ transformation through wide-scale revolt against state and market, while bringing in radical alternatives; ‘symbiotic’ transformation is through long term co-operation with existing structures and institutions (e.g. trade unions); while ‘interstitial’ transformations take a prefigurative approach, by creating future alternatives in the here and now. Regarding SI and post-capitalist transformations, interstitial transformations aid us in their conceptualization,

by seeking to create new forms of social empowerment within the niches and margins of capitalism, while building social power through civil society, they mirror many features of the grassroots conceptions of SI.

To give these re-conceptualizations of SI further analytical power, we draw on Assemblage thinking (Deleuze & Guattari, 1980). The main contribution of assemblage is analysing socio-spatial phenomena and understanding them relationally as dynamic wholes, in constant flux, or becoming. Rather than their essential qualities, it gives priority to relations and qualities, enabling a mode of analysis where we can compare bodies through their given affective relations, (Buchanan, 1997). The term ‘assemblage’ is a translation from the French - *agencement* - originally applied by Deleuze and Guattari to signify the capacity to act. *Agencement* holds more meaning than the English ‘assemblage’, including to arrange, to dispose to fit up, to combine, to order (Law, 2004: 41). Therefore, while assemblages are made up of material, expressive and symbolic components, we must look at them beyond a collection of things but their interaction, arrangement, ordering and (dis)assembly. Moreover, we must look beyond the components themselves, which are just the “props needed to actualize a particular arrangement of desire.” (Buchanan, 1997: 65), thus assemblages are desire driven.

Following other approaches drawing from Deleuze & Guattari in trying to understand SI, we want to highlight the rhizomatic nature of social relations (Pel *et al.*, 2020; Scott-Cato & Hillier, 2010). Rather than essentializing SI processes, we view changing social relations as a non-linear, rhizomatic process that occurs through the culmination of everyday actions, without a necessary beginning or end. Rhizomatic change is a micropolitics of becoming, that seeks to open new possibilities and multiplicities, towards post-capitalist futures. We want to “*focus on process rather than on product, on struggle and deliberation rather than on an image of a predefined collective identity or geographical locality.*” (Gibson-Graham *et al.*, 2020: 5).

Moreover, throughout the analysis we will draw heavily from the concept of affect, understood as the capacity to affect and be affected. When bodies enter affective relations with one another, it refers to those ‘encounters’ that may augment, or diminish their respective capacities (Slaby & Mühlhoff, 2019). This is central to our assemblage analysis, as we will demonstrate how various (human and non-human, material and expressive) component parts affect the assemblage and its capacities. This autonomy of parts can also be referred to as the exteriority of relations (DeLanda, 2006). Affective labour (Hardt, 1999) understood as the production and manipulation of affects, will also be essential to our understanding of the CWS role in organizing social relations, and subject formation, as individual capacities are made, unmade and re-made (Slaby & Mühlhoff, 2019).

CWS

CWS refers to spaces, which are primarily work purposed environments, but they can also be places where people come together for both work and other personal activities in a shared space such as coworking spaces, makerspaces, fab-labs, business incubators and accelerators, social and cultural centres etc. (Schmidt & Brinks, 2017). CWS have been described as sites of ambivalence, demonstrating tensions between both corporate and counter-corporate, capitalistic and commonsing, collaborative and individualistic ways of being (Bandinelli & Arvidsson, 2013; De Peuter *et al.*, 2017; Vidaillet & Bousalham, 2020). This contrast displays the plurality of CWS, the term may relate to work collectives, co-operatives for freelancers and other forms in response to precarious markets, which operate with values of the social and solidarity economy; or alternatively CWS may act as business incubators or accelerators for start-ups, along with corporate chains of coworking (Arvidsson, 2020; Brooke *et al.*, 2014; De Peuter *et al.*, 2017). Contributions generally differentiate between entrepreneurial-led vs community-led CWS (Avdikos & Iliopoulou, 2019; Avdikos & Merkel, 2020), with the latter also referred to as resilient CWS (Gandini & Cossu, 2021). While both types overlap in their activities and functions (Avdikos & Pettas, 2021), community led CWS generally are not-for-profit, and have an authentic concern for their community (Avdikos & Iliopoulou, 2019).

Moreover, there is a growing number of contributions referring to the political economy of CWS, and their potential for fostering alternative economic practices (e.g. Smith (2020); Vidaillet & Bousalham, 2020). While not always offering a complete alternative to the market, it appears that a number of community led CWS may oscillate between the market and the commons (Avdikos & Pettas, 2021). For example, while CWS may rent out office space for freelancers, they may simultaneously offer their space to be used by the local community (e.g. neighbourhood associations) for events and other services (Brown, 2017).

More recently, the CWS phenomena has diffused to rural and peripheral areas, yet questions remain about how their dynamics may both compare and contrast to their urban counterparts. Multiple sources (e.g. Görmar, 2021; Tomaz *et al.*, 2022) have highlighted that CWS in rural areas are more diverse in the activities they offer than urban CWS, ranging from community services to social and cultural initiatives. Through offering a range of services, such CWS can act as a ‘social hub’, or ‘social infrastructure of care’ for communities, by both creating and maintaining the social fabric of rural areas (Avdikos & Merkel, 2020; Marmo & Avdikos, 2024; Merkel, 2023).

Community-led CWS can facilitate grassroots innovation practices when used by local citizens to address local social needs (Dias & Smith, 2018). These CWS thus can be used as

a tool to foster economic diversity (Gibson-Graham, 2008; Smith, 2020) by engaging in simultaneous capitalist, alternative and non-capitalist practices, and they can act as ‘syntopias’ for their communities (Vidaillet & Bousalham, 2020).

Methods

The research applied a qualitative case study approach (Yin, 2018). Data collection was carried out for roughly one month in each case, between March to June 2023. A key informant (the manager of the CWS) was used to gain access to the CWS, local people and various activities and events that took place during the stay. The study applied qualitative research methods: i) participatory observation, ii) semi-structured interviews, and iii) focus groups. The researcher engaged in a total of over 3,000 hours of participant observation, with the role changing throughout the data collection period, from a ‘participating observer’, ‘partially participating observer’ and ‘minimally participating observer’ (Bryman, 2012), depending on the situation. Observations were supported by 30 semi-structured interviews as a means of understanding how individuals experience and make sense of their own lives. Interviews were conducted with those directly involved with the CWS (e.g. managers, workers, volunteers, individuals and groups who use the services, such as institutional partners, and those indirectly involved with the CWS (e.g. locals who do not use the CWS). Prior to fieldwork, a research proposal was submitted and approved by the ethics committee at Panteion University. (Protocol Number: 44/ 30-9-2022). In line with ethics guidelines, the names of the interview participants and CWS have pseudonymized to protect the identities of those who participated in the study.

Case studies

For reasons of anonymity, we call the Greek case Western Greece Hub (WGH) and Austrian case Collaborate Upper Austria (CUA). While research took place in two small towns in the regions of Western Greece and Upper Austria, just the regions will be referred to. WGH is a non-profit organization founded as a legal entity in 2019. The organization emerged from a former local activist group concerned about the downward trajectory of the town. Their purpose is to strengthen the collectivity in the local community through the participatory mapping of the city and its culture, preserving its environmental wealth and the creation of programs of alternative cultural tourism and ecotourism. Since 2019 the organization has a ‘Local Hub’ which acts as a node for community activities of the town. Among their many activities include a gift shop with local products, boat tours, art classes, creative activities for children, providing a meeting point for groups, Info Point, an annual cultural festival, free tours of historical and cultural sites, and an educational programme focused on the ecological and cultural heritage of their town in collaboration with several schools. They co-operate with other local community organizations for example art galleries, museums, hiking group and a fishing co-operative. It is run and managed by its founder, and currently employ 2 staff members, 3 at the time of data collection. Additionally, it relies on many volunteers and informal labour and transactions for many of their activities.

CUA is both a workers’ cooperative and network of associations in rural Austria. Initially founded as an association in 2010 with the idea of free open space for experimentation, funded through the municipality. While there are several CUA associations, the study is focused on one location in a small village in Upper Austria, located in a technical school. The co-operative (CUA Co-op) emerged out of the association, in 2014, as the volunteer members of the CUA association began to take on larger projects that required lots of time, thus paid labour. The co-op is a workers co-operative, composed of individual member-owners and employees, with a focus on project-based work. In this particular case study, the lines between both sometimes are blurred, as some are members of both the associations and the co-op. The coop provides a lot of resources to the association, who rely on support from the municipality for its functioning, while it also receives donations from individuals and businesses. For clarity, ‘CUA’ will refer to the CUA association, and the CUA co-op will be stated when referring to the co-operative. The co-op, may be regarded as a form of social innovation, however, this study wants to understand SI processes through hubs, and for the sake of comparison it was better to focus on the association.

CUA offers firstly an open space for people (young and old) to meet, socialize, and share their ideas. Through this mix, they have been able ‘activate’ local people to share knowledge and be open to new ideas. This has also given rise to a number of new associations or businesses. CUA collaborates with many institutional partners, municipalities, businesses, schools, banks, local businesses.

Description of the localities. The case studies are two small towns in Western Greece (population 14,386), and Upper Austria (7,602). Table 1 shows the stark economic contrast between the two regions, with Austria higher on economic indicators, with a GDP per capita in Upper Austria almost four times than that of the region of Western Greece.

While it would be easy to present and compare the classic economic based differences between the two countries, this study aims to explore the contextual environments and how this leads to different arrangements of SI, while also acknowledging the very different starting points across the world for enacting post-capitalist possibility. In Austria we have a strong market economy, with lots of state support for projects and regional development. In Greece, we see the opposite, with rural areas lacking in markets and state support, however informal activities play an important part in everyday life. Here we will present the two ‘local assemblages’, a complex assemblage of past and present, stories, institutions, culture, economies, knowledges and heritage that combine to create the local assemblage (Willett, 2013)

Western greece

The regional demographics table shows that it has a GDP per capita almost 7,000€ lower than the rest of the country, a lower employment rate by 4% and is 10% higher regarding persons at risk of poverty or social exclusion (JRC, 2024).

Table 1. Regional Demographics of the two regions in comparison to the country average (JRC, 2024).

Regional Demographics					
	Region of Western Greece (EL63)	Greece Average	Upper Austria (AT31)	Austria Average	EU 27 Average
Population	639, 500	10.4 million	1.53 million	9.1. million	NA
GDP per Capita at current prices	16, 520	23, 450	59, 580	57, 830	40, 810
Employment rate %	62.4	63.3	80.8	77.3	74.6
% of persons at risk of poverty or social exclusion	40.9	30	11.6 (2018)	17.5 (2020)	NA

This is a common feature of the Greek periphery, with most economic activity concentrated in Athens. More specifically, the town in question suffers from a narrative of decline, the effect of several events, shocks, policies among other factors. Literature on rural areas describes how these events collectively form a ‘vicious circle of decline’ that lead to their peripheralization (Bock, 2016). Prior to 2018, the town and its economy were centred around a university with 5000 students, through hospitality services and student accommodation. However, as part of austerity measures, the national university system became more centralized, and most of the university’s departments were relocated to Patras, the closest city. Now only 500 students remain, representing a 90% decline. This had a significant impact on the economy, something that is clear if you take a walk through the main streets and observe all the ‘for rent’ and ‘for sale’ signs on former commercial buildings.

Despite the negativity and lack of opportunities, the area has an abundance of natural beauty. It is located on a large lagoon, which provides a natural habitat to several migratory birds and aquatic life such as eels and various fish. Fishing is part of the local culture, with fishermen living in a unique style of house on the water called *pelada*, with similarly unique fishing technique for the lagoon using netted pools and specialized netted boats. The town also is significant site for Greek national heritage, with it being one of the last sites of resistance against the Ottoman Empire in 1826. The siege is recognized as an important event towards gaining of Greek independence. It is celebrated yearly with a week of festivities and is heavily supported by the municipality. As its located on the open water, it has historically been open to many different types of people and cultures. People are very proud of their history, and of their town. There is a specific accent and words only used in the area, a book at the hub referred to this, with over 200 phrases particular to the local area. Tourism is seen as having big potential by many to save the towns economic fortunes; however it is clear some capacity is lacking to accommodate for them, there is a large hotel that is not fit for purpose, appearing derelict, mirroring what one interviewee described as one of many ‘almost places’ in the town.

Upper Austria

In Upper Austria, we have quite a different picture. The GDP is higher than the national average (€59,580 compared with €57, 830), employment is also higher (80.8% compared to 77.3%). Generally, the town appears to be doing ‘development’ right, the area is growing with new houses being built and lots of industry close by that provides plenty of jobs, and a relatively new motorway beside the village that links with nearby cities of Linz, Wels and Salzburg, and relatively well-connected public transport, given its peripherality. Located within the region of Upper Austria, it is part of one of the 2024 European Capitals of Culture, Salzkammergut. It is a very small village, of just over 7,000 inhabitants, yet functions as a commercial centre for surrounding towns and villages, with a couple of supermarkets, some restaurants, a bank, school, and a church. It is very clear that there is a lot of material wealth, it’s common to see swimming pools in people’s back gardens, nice cars, while electric bicycles can be seen cycling around.

However, there are social issues that affect the village, mainly an ageing population, and a lack of young people. One reason given for the decline of young people was the lack of services and activities that address the youth that does live there. Others noted the educational options, as the village has a technical school but not ‘Gymnasium’ second level school (more focused on academic education, sciences, languages etc.), which can cause children to leave at a very young age and lose ties with the village. Participants also spoke of a lack of public investment in public infrastructure, such as the school. Moreover, there are traditional and conservative values that some people can find constraining, such as views on gender roles, or politics (such as a conservative government in the region) that progressive people saw as problematic.

Similarly to the Greek case, there is a specific Austrian dialect (more particular to the region than the place), although it does not have that specific local history and culture as the Greek case. It shares regional traditions, such as on Sundays it was common to see people dressed in traditional Austrian attire, men in ‘Lederhosen’ and women in ‘Dirndl’. The uniform for women working in the traditional Gasthaus’s is this

traditional attire. People gather once a week in the Markthall for a market with local products. However, some interviewees explained that despite being well connected, local cultures and traditions are not shared between towns and villages in the region. Therefore, these narratives still mirror some of the classic depiction of rural areas, lacking in state investment, declining services and infrastructure supports, traditional values (Edensor, 2006).

Findings section

CWS and local social needs

What is quite clear in Western Greece, is that many of its social problems are structural. The main problems that people stressed were rubbish (not being collected, public littering) and poor infrastructure – physical (e.g. roads) and social (e.g. places for exercise, playgrounds for kids). These material problems, they feed into the immaterial, regarding the feeling of inertia, narrative of decline, and people not taking responsibility about the town's problems. This is what WGH aims to address, the founder stresses that “we cannot build roads, or deal with stray dogs so they don't bite people” and that addressing these problems are the responsibility of the municipality to fix. This is shown through how WGH sometimes organize community clean ups of the lagoon, but don't want to organize it regularly, as they would be doing the municipality's job for them.

Rather than directly address the material problems of their town, the CWS addresses the immaterial element, as is clear in other SI initiatives (Chen *et al.*, 2022). They aim to bring change rhizomatically, through everyday actions rather than the big events that are seen as providing economic development for the town by the municipality. While such events create a buzz, both in their duration and towards their build up, on normal days there is nothing happening, and the town feels empty.

MBL plugs itself into the local assemblage, one which was described above through having interesting history, culture, and traditions. They use the expressive and semiotic components of the local assemblage, and combine them with their vision of the town, and what it could be. For example, they offer engraving classes (a traditional practice from the area) where participants can engrave from photographs of the lagoon and the fisherman's dwellings, or something else if they would like. They are very active on social media, always capturing a sunset or candid pictures of the lagoon.

They listen to their community to understand their needs. For example, the creative children's activities exist because it was requested by parents. The creative activities vary weekly and can include making paper, creating notebooks, painting, animation workshops, screen printing to name a few. The founder explained that when he was younger, creative activities were scarce, there was only football and he had no idea you could be an artist, a photographer, a graphic designer etc. Along with being creative and learning new skills, the

workshops are aimed to get the children working together. They try to pair older kids with younger, passing on the knowledge the older ones have learned in the classes. The hub also acts as a meeting point. While hosting different events and exhibitions, the different activities that take place more regularly act as an excuse for locals to meet and chat. It was very common for parents of kids to gather outside the hub on a Saturday with a coffee after they collected or dropped off their children. One day the founder described it as a cafe because of all the comings and goings. On some occasions people would stop by and discuss everyday matters, such as local politics, planning for the upcoming festival, or to give out about the available mezze options in the town. Thus, the CWS acts as an important and much needed meeting and focal point, and social infrastructure (Klinenberg, 2018) for the town, along with providing creative activities that are also lacking.

It acts as a place where different people who would not normally cross paths can meet. Their activities address all ages, some engraving groups had participants ranging from 14 to 70. They have an oral history group that aims to retain oral traditions of the town, remembering specific people and events. They also collaborate with an ecologist and a local fisherman's collective to provide an educational programme for children, working with several local schools.

These activities are provided to address the local needs of the community but are part of a bigger picture. They form part of a larger whole, an arrangement of desire, which, as shown before, is territorialised through the combination of different local components, such as local culture and natural resources. WHG has a vision of a future that it wants to produce. Their vision and desire for the town is one that is flourishing, where people take an active role in society, not “waiting for the great mayor” (Quote from interview with the manager) to come and fix things, but through small everyday actions they can construct a better future. Regarding their economic struggles, they see slow tourism as a solution. However, beyond the economic, they want a vibrant cultural life, people to care for and understand the environment, have local people engaged in activities outside their job and be involved in community activities. Through the existence of the CWS and its activities they offer a window into the future they desire to create – a community economy.

In CUA, we see a similar arrangement of desire. While they do not focus on local culture and traditions, they also make use of several material (e.g. technology) and expressive (e.g. open and collaborative ethos, ‘play’ mentality) to do so. While the local ‘economy’ is strong, they are lacking in some of the ‘social’ aspects of life. Despite local associations existing - music groups, a football club, photography, church groups etc, they were described by one CUA member as only having older people, closed and competitive. CUA is the opposite, promoting youth involvement, being open and collaborative.

Furthermore, the CWS has an alternative view on economy, and is more explicit regarding its political subjectivity, with the CUA co-op being a member-owned co-operative. Their impact report critiques the endless growth-and-innovation society we find ourselves in, and that CUA ‘*challenges this through the creation of resonant connections between people, things and the world*’ (CUA Impact report, 2020). The municipality is an essential component, without which the model of free open space would not function, as the municipality pays its bills and provides it with public infrastructure to use.

This subjectivity plays a key role in territorializing their assemblage, and broader societal change is much more present in their narratives rather than the focus on local development by WGH. However, they are not ideological, nor rigid politically and collaborate with actors they would otherwise criticize such as various municipal, state, and market actors (e.g. commercial banks). The social change they envision, is a collaborative over divisive, one where people are active in civil society, and not only focused on waged work, hence their suitability for transitions to post-capitalism (Chatterton & Pusey, 2020). They have a focus on ‘new work’, inspired by the work of Frithjof Bergmann believing life should be split between paid work, community work, and leisure time to pursue one’s interests. The members of the co-op mainly live in this way, through self-employment, community work for the co-op through workshops or community activities in the association, while using their free time to ‘do what they really, really want’. Their activities are open to anyone in the community to join, and they have a full schedule of activities running that can be accessed online – art classes, technology classes for the elderly, repair café, woodwork, climate action group. Most of the focus is ‘being-in-common’, without competition, the need to succeed or achieve anything, as one interviewee highlighted.

They have a long history collaboration with the school, something that was addressed as a problem for the area – both the type of school it is (a technical school) and that it is old. Through their connections with industry, CUA co-operative provided over twenty 3D printers to the school, which are now integrated into the curriculum. They also have co-operated with certain teachers, doing different projects related to technology and independent thinking, and run similar projects funded by the regional authority with younger kids in preschool.

In both CWS, people form an essential component of their assemblage. In both locations, the CWS assemble interesting and unconventional people, that normally either are forgotten/left invisible in a small town, those who do not ‘fit in’ in the highly territorialized and codified (homogenous) small town. It seems the unconventional people can easier comprehend the change they wish to make, or they themselves desire change to a more open and inclusive society.

They both make sure they do not just employ anyone but want to ensure they have the same mindset and perspective, the

same coding to ensure the territorialization of the CWS assemblage. In WHG, before hiring the staff, they were asked to write a personal essay on the town and the hub, why they think it is important. One of the staff members mentioned how he felt a magnetic attraction to the hub, as their goals are the same as his personal goals. In CUA, when looking to hire a new employee for the eGen, they put out an advertisement searching for someone “*who is able to use a truck, able to work with wood material, who is open minded and able to have an open and mindful conversation with people.*” (Interviewee 1)

Moreover, both CWS have two leading figures that act as gatekeepers of the assemblage. Both may be considered as social entrepreneurs, and have a considerable impact on the assemblage, providing it with many affects. Such is common in SI initiatives, to have certain key individuals at the core of the assemblage (Richter & Christmann, 2021).

Changing social relations

In this section, we examine ‘changing social relations’, the second dimension of SI, considering the relational character of social relations through the concept of affect. Here we will explore how individual subjectivities transform into collective through the CWS. In both cases they do a lot of work to create community and increase collaboration. In Greece, the lack of collectivity in the periphery comes from a lack of trust in each other and institutions, often because of clientelist relations. In the Austrian periphery, while there exists strong institutional trust, there are a lack of places for socializing outside of the traditional meeting points or commercial venues. In both cases it was clear that many individuals lacked some form of a purpose in life, outside of their economic role. The CWS open space for diverse economic activities, on two separate, but related levels. Firstly, on the material level through praxis and secondly on the immaterial level in terms of people’s perceptions. Changing social relations and the subsequent increasing of affects and capacities towards community interests forms an essential part in the part of becoming post-capitalist subjects (Gabriel & Sarmiento, 2020). Moreover, these actions have a dual character, as they also provide the CWS’ with affects and help with its everyday reproduction – an affective relation.

Desiring Production and assisting with capacities. The CWS’s play a key role in desiring production, i.e. they help actors to create something (be it economic, social, or other). Both CWS’s act as nodes that give actors opportunities to affect and be affected, by providing them with resources, generally without charge, such as space, knowledge, materials, networks, equipment etc. that increases their capacities, and enables them to bring desires into reality, or in assemblage terms, desiring production. Part of their association comes from the ability of the CWS to provide meaning making, or axes of resonance (Rosa, 2019) through non-alienated and significant relationships with the world and with others. Rosa (2019: 171) identifies resonance as a basic human capacity and need, and that all human desire, is a desire for resonance. It is

this aspect that gives CUA's motto – 'CUA does not do anything, CUA makes possible'. This highlights how the CWS innovate not in an economic or technical sense but as *innovation in social relations*. They create and aid in the creation of new collaborations in places against the narrative that nothing is happening. We can regard this as SI practice, or outputs of SI processes (Moulaert & Mehmood, 2020). It also highlights how the three dimensions of SI (addressing social needs, changing social relations and collective empowerment) are closely intertwined (Moulaert & MacCallum, 2019). By addressing the needs of the local community (inertia in this case), they increase actors' agency changing social relations and empower them with collective sense of identity.

One interesting example of this comes from an art teacher/artist, who first moved to Western Greece during COVID, working as a substitute art teacher. He initially found the CWS to meet local people, and once getting familiar with the CWS' activities, collaborated with them for an engraving summer school, which evolved into workshop in the CWS's annual festival, and later a workshop as part of their environmental educational programme with local schools. The teacher noted all these activities as being very important to him, improving his skills, and doing meaningful work. The hub also gained new capacities through the affective relation through gaining an art teacher to run weekly printmaking workshops and an artistic element to their educational program. The atmosphere of the CWS benefited, as the art teacher is a character and would call in frequently for small chats and gossip. An interesting observation is how this affective relation can affect the larger whole, the local community. From participating in the annual festival of the hub, it gave visibility to the art teacher, and he was approached by a local NGO that does artistic workshops with young kids and children with disabilities. In addition, through the educational programme, this affective relation offered an interesting solution to combat the lack of artistic infrastructure in the Greek public school system: Their solution entailed using the CWS as an art space, as part of their environmental education program –

“from my point of view, this is how the school has to be. An art classroom, which is ready, and when I want to do a lesson I will have my projector, my materials, the cabinet, every child will have his corner, his seat, a room filled with drawings or experiments that children have done before... here we have found, I am certain, we have found the solution to that problem.” (Teacher, interview)

There were several other examples of the CWS collaborating with local people to help realize their desires, such as giving sound equipment to owners of a local tavern on their re-opening night (a big night for the town), helping an elderly woman publish a children's book and giving a young girl books, links and historical information about the town, in order for her to do a presentation to 150 people about a historical event, where the hub marketed the event,

provided her with lights and sound equipment to make it happen.

Regarding staff, it used to employ two artists; one of them left and the other could no longer be paid because of the end of a state funding programme. However, this affective relation was incredibly important for the CWS, for the town to retain two young artists, and for the artists themselves, who could have employment in their hometown, develop their careers as artists, and do meaningful work (e.g. with children, the environment). As one interviewee stated, “[artist 1] and [artist 2] are kids that probably the town would have nothing to do if the hub did not exist”. The CWS and the town gained two artists, who pass on their knowledge to young kids. The mutual benefit was highlighted when one artist took part in a prominent Greek animation festival, and the organizers came to do an animation workshop with young kids. Moreover, despite them leaving, the CWS is still interested in their professional and personal development, and they still collaborate on projects when they have the time and funding.

We see a similar picture in CUA, at the core of what they do is allowing people to follow their ideas and interests, helping people to find “*what they really, really want*” to do. This happens through CUA's model of free open space where people can encounter new activities and interesting people. Sometimes this happens to the extent that people can follow ideas into a funded project, generally from municipal, regional, or national funds. For example, For example, the CWS has a climate action group that started meeting informally to create a discussion about renewable energy in the town, they have since carried out several renewable energy projects in several public buildings, funded by the municipality. Another project between CUA, the school and the European Capital of Culture funds entailed schoolkids working with CUA in groups to realize their ideas (such as a film night with friends, hosted in CUA). On occasions an informal group forms into a more coherent body, for example a food co-operative was incubated there, also a company that makes 3D printers. On the individual level, CUA can unlock desires that otherwise would not have been possible living in a small town. One of their employees began his relationship with CUA as a teenager, taking part in a soldering workshop, He since has a degree in computer science and works on technology projects with the CUA eGen co-operative. He credits CUA for him following this career path.

Here we can see the CWS's acting as a relational tool, creating new relationships between locals. They act as a middle ground, assembling different actors, with material (e.g. equipment) and immaterial (e.g. funding, knowledge) components they previously would not have access to, that enables them to realize their own projects, achieving their own desires. And almost all these happen in the framework of diverse and community economies, with affective labour as a core codification and resource.

From the individual to the affective community. SI theory tells us how SI processes can lead to collective empowerment by changing social relations from individual to community needs (Gibson-Graham & Roelvink, 2009). This section aims to unravel how this occurs in the CWS assemblages, as individuals encounter the CWS, they form part of the CWS' affective community (Zink, 2019). The CWS affective community is not the classic internal paid-membership form as is found in more market orientated CWS but expands outside their walls. The relationality (Escobar, 2021) of the CWS describes their ability to keep creating connections with humans and non-humans, recognising radical interdependence based on care and respect.

For example, WGH, as noted before, organizes an annual festival, with a focus on local culture, heritage, and traditions they create an affective arrangement that forms a collective identity. Given their lack of resources to employ the number of workers needed to plan and manage the festival, they make use of the affective labour of the local community to help them. The festival activities, like much of the CWS' everyday activities create positive affects for the town, not only for the CWS, with workshops about local culture and traditions, history, kayaking on the lagoon, hiking the surrounding mountains, art exhibitions, concert among many others. These actions create a bond between the locals and their place, and the variety of actors that inhabit it. The festival acts as a temporary arrangement of desire enacted, bringing together collective action and affective labour to create a window into what could be for the town, if everybody pooled together, highlighting what is possible in a diverse community economy.

In CUA, they also change social relations towards collective subjectivities through affective labour. The monthly repair café in CUA epitomizes this. The members of the group offer their labour, knowledge, and materials to the community for free, while they collaborate with other repair cafes nearby to share materials and ensure they don't clash timetables. Their impact report states how these practices of repair *are intended to contribute to self-efficacy and self-empowerment, going beyond the relationship of consumption with objects.* Another interesting group was the 'death café' where people would meet up and talk about death, changing a typically individual and personal subject into a collective one –

“something I loved was the death café, where people talked about death for hours.. Just about the topic death. What do you think about death? What do you think about and how do you experience? What experience do you have with death and the setup was sitting around drinking coffee, eating cake and discussing death. I like the setup and the chance to talk about topics where you don't have the chance to talk about it at home with, the people you love.”

(Interviewee 2)

This collaborative ethos is also apparent with the many collaborators each CWS has. By being open, and not focused

on profit, their ethos is reciprocated. As one CUA member stated, *“if you're generous to people, normally people are generous the other way around”*. In CUA, they often receive donations of equipment that they can either use for parts for repair, or in the organization such as laptops, coffee machines, and kitchen utensils. These practices can manifest change at the individual level, forming new collective subjectivities, as people want to contribute to the community economy. One interviewee, formerly the chairwoman of the association, noted how being part of CUA affected her own ways of thinking, how old buildings can be used to benefit the community:

And the thing is that the CUA philosophy changed my work within the community or is influencing how I see things in the community, like having a lost place or an unused house that we can do there something without money, and what to do in social life.

(Interviewee 3)

In WGH, because of their relatively lower financial capacities, donations can have a higher impact. The organization was gifted a drone for videoing the lagoon, a telescope for birdwatching, a new phone for taking high quality photos, something which greatly increased their capacities and allows them to reach more people and become more professionalized.

More than just changing relations among their community, the CWS's influence other larger assemblages with their open and collective way of doing things. We may understand how CWS's affect other assemblages, through the concept of relations of exteriority, that each component part of the assemblage is autonomous, and can form part of other assemblages. Through collaboration with schools, and their existing relationships with the environmentalist and fishermen, they created a programme to address the lack of connection with locals and the natural environment, and the poor infrastructure of the public schools in Greece. Recognizing the exteriority of relations allows them to teach the schoolkids, inform them, and allow them to bring their knowledge into other assemblages, such as their families, and other groups they are part of, something Avdikos & Pettas (2021) refer to as diffusion of the CWS collaborative culture to broader circuits.

WGH educate the public about the local environment and its importance for the town, that it's not a distant far away thing or merely a resource to be exploited. They work with the fishing co-operative, who fish seasonally, but the rest of the year still must operate the 'Divari' (traditional fishing structure) to maintain the lagoon, keeping it clean and refreshing it with enough clean water. The ecologist explained how only the co-operative does this maintenance work, and there is an issue with private fishermen trying to win fishing rights, who only fish for profit rather than working with the lagoon and the environment. Through this education, WGH reframes the relationship between the 'hegemonic trio' of economy-society-environment (Miller, 2019), not as separate spheres of life, but as interconnected and contingent on one another with a collection of human and non-human actants that co-exist and co-depend in the same geographical space.

In the case of CUA, they have a long-standing relationship with both the municipality and the local school, spanning over 10 years. Their relationship with the municipality has the agreement that the municipality will pay for the space and its maintenance, but will not interfere with it in any way, that it is free of party politics, and they should not expect any kind of output or results. The CWS focus is on the local community, and therefore, like WGH, the value it creates is not for the CWS, but for the town. Adhering to the exteriority of relations allows the CWS' to penetrate other assemblages, and to 'infiltrate' other more strictly coded and highly territorialized assemblages, such as schools and municipalities, while maintaining their own autonomy and not adhering to their codes.

Through this symbiosis the school also benefits from their existence, through shared projects, a summer school and donation of 3D printers. The local community also benefits from the re-coding of property to the community through the opening of public property outside of school hours. For example, a wood turning group uses the woodwork room. While initially difficult to understand, one teacher explained how it changed their own perceptions about the school infrastructure:

you know it's only for the short period when it's being used, then actually for the majority of the day it's completely empty.... this was this was new for us, but some ones come in my arts room. It's not my arts room, but I thought about it. Why do I react in this way?

The emancipatory of the potential of these practices lies in these two levels of changing social relations, desiring production (praxis) and changing individual to collective subjectivities. This is emancipatory and transformative as it destabilizes what Deleuze and Guattari describe as the machinic unconscious, unlocking a revolution of micropolitical becoming in those that encounter the CWS's. Rather than being subjected to machinic enslavement and inertia, the CWS's offer liberation from the circuits of the machines at play in both localities, be it through the 'left-behindness' in Greece or lack of purpose in Austria. The use of affective labour has transformative potential, as it creates collective subjectivities, social networks, community, and biopower from below (Hardt, 1999).

Discussion: the transformative potential of CWS

The third dimension of SI, according to Moolaert & MacCallum (2019) is 'socio-political transformative potential'. We would like to understand the type of transformation the CWS's enact is enabling 'intentional economies' in the words of Gibson-Graham (2008) or 'real utopias' as Wright emphasised (2010). Both represent open ended post-capitalist realities, by facilitating pluriversity (Escobar, 2021) or economic diversity (Gibson-Graham, 2008), working towards creating many different worlds, rather than the perceived dominant capitalist world, destabilizing its perceived hegemony. Rather than providing an exact post-capitalist strategy, the CWS provide a "multitude of possibilities of what could come

after, as well as building daily competences to leverage social change." (Chatterton, 2016: 405)". Moving beyond certainty, we aim to provide one potential pathway of many possibilities towards creating such a future. To do so, we would like to infuse Wright's thinking with that of DCE, understanding social transformation as post-capitalism, and Wright's three types of transformation, as three stages of transformation.

As highlighted in the literature review section of the paper, Wright provides three pathways towards social transformation – *ruptural, interstitial and symbiotic*. Interstitial transformation may be the social transformation most closely linked to grassroots SI, referring to the 'various kinds of processes that occur in the spaces and cracks within some dominant social structure of power' (p. 229). Wright gives examples of interstitial transformations such as various forms of co-ops, workers councils, community based social economy organizations etc., which are also common examples of SI. Such initiatives offer viable alternatives to state and capitalist ways of organizing, however, are often critiqued as operating in isolation, whereby they do not offer a real viable alternative, but merely as heterotopias that operate within 'niche' or 'protective spaces' (Smith & Raven, 2012). This is what we conceptualize as our first level of transformation, which we can clearly see as the two CWS's work towards satisfying community needs and build community economies, through desiring production and building affective relations.

Both spaces act as heterotopias, or syntopias (Vidaillet & Bousalham, 2020), that allow users to experience other ways of being in the world. While both hubs offer this, CUA is more explicit about its interstitial function of the space – "we have, kind of research Lab to try out things outside of the normal economic, a free space where it's not based on the normal ongoing system status and that was one of the basic ideas with CUA to create the spaces, to create ideas. Maybe for the future. Maybe it is quite small, but maybe change something if we need." (CUA co-founder, interview).

Regarding symbiotic transformations, Wright differentiates them from interstitial mainly due to their orientation towards the state, which they use as a mediating body to reduce capitalist power, with the main example given as class compromise, where workers and capitalist firms negotiate through the state over workers' rights, pay etc. However, we would like to offer a different conceptualization of symbiotic transformation, as a second stage of interstitial transformation diffusion, as they influence other spatiotemporal arrangements. This may initially be in antagonism, and lead to their practices being copied/replicated by state or municipal organizations, or it may mean these institutions recognising and supporting interstitial transformations as important social economy actors. In both cases we also observe this level of transformation, with long term institutional collaboration of CUA and the municipality and more recently in WGH as they have begun to collaborate with the new municipality through organizing a public consultation regarding the town's development. Moreover, both CWS also offer their resources

and capacities to local actors such as schools, local businesses and other market entities, NGOs, and other local associations, blending DCE economies with the market economy. While interstitial transformation through the DCE framework is usually performed inside the CWS, symbiotic transformation happens outside the bounded environment of CWS and offers to other entities and the state to experience the alternative socio-economic arrangements, through the DCE framework that CWS's assemblages perform.

Within SI literature, SI is often deemed to be transformative when it pierces this institutional level (Haxeltine *et al.*, 2016; Moulaert & MacCallum, 2019), when SI bottom-up initiatives are supported by institutions, it is referred to as bottom-linked SI that “develops when citizens’ collective initiatives result in agreements with local institutions that enable and sustain such initiatives through sound, regulated and lasting practices” (Garcia *et al.*, 2015: 93). This symbiotic approach has many merits and is key for SI’s transformative potential to move beyond their space in the margins. However, SI being recognized by institutions does not equate to the neoliberal rhetoric by governments over the last twenty years (for example see Fougère *et al.*, 2017 for a full discussion), something that ‘limits social innovation to marginal change’ (Bartels, 2017). Initiatives need to be given resources and power rather than just responsibility (Bragaglia, 2021). Moreover, through symbiosis it allows us to move beyond the binary of initiatives either rejecting institutions or being co-opted by them, allowing for real change to be enacted and further institutionalized (Bartels, 2017).

Figure 1 demonstrates how as DCE practices are performed and practiced, moving from the edifices and margins as interstitial

Figure 1. How Diverse and Community Economy practices diffuse throughout the three levels of transformation.

transformations, to piercing the institutional dimension, and beyond we envisage CE practices spreading in a form of contagion until they reach a saturation point of post-capitalist becoming, signifying not necessarily a straight clean break from capitalism to post-capitalism, but a revolution of becoming, as different aspects of life become recoded and DCE are heavily territorialized and enacted in society. Both cases do not reflect this level of transformation (yet, at least), but an example of such a ‘real utopia’ would be the widely documented case of Mondragon in the Basque country, with the co-operative model completely institutionalized in the region. While as an example it is highly contextual and non-replicable, it gives an example of possibility (Gibson-Graham, 2008). We cannot state this is the case for either case studies, both remain still in their symbiotic stage. The passage to a ruptural transformation requires CWS to be supported by various local and extra-local actors to be acknowledged as the only alternative and post-capitalist solution, where DCE can become the dominant mode of production and gain a hegemonic place in society.

Conclusion

The paper discussed the role of CWS as initiators and facilitators of SI processes in two community led CWS in two rural areas in Austria and Greece. The research methodology employed a qualitative case study approach, utilizing participant observation and semi-structured interviews to explore the multiple sets of relations found in these rural CWS, aiming to understand how these arrangements cover local needs and foster new social relations. The findings reveal that CWS play a significant role in addressing social needs and facilitating grassroots SI practices, creating affective relations that contribute to the transformation of individual to collective subjectivities. CWS seem to provide a site where the unmet needs of the local people are negotiated, redefined and are covered in a co-creative and collective manner. This is happening in a DCE framework, where affective labour mostly performs.

CWS have a significant impact on individual subjectivities by transforming them into collective subjectivities through affective relations and desiring production, through the implementation of collaborative projects. The CWS play a crucial role in changing social relations and increasing affects and capacities towards community interests, which is an essential part of becoming post-capitalist subjects. They provide opportunities for actors to affect and be affected, increasing their agency and assisting them with their own desires by providing resources such as space, knowledge, materials, networks, and equipment. This process enables desiring production and creates non-alienated and significant relationships with the world and with others, which is essential for subject formation and the development of collective subjectivities.

Furthermore, the affective relations formed within CWS’s have a transformative potential, as they create new collaborations and relationships in places where the narrative that

nothing is happening. These affective relations also extend to the larger community in a symbiotic manner, creating positive affects for the town and fostering collective action and affective labor to create a window into what could be for the community. Additionally, the CWS's influence other larger assemblages through the concept of relations of exteriority, allowing them to 'infiltrate' other more strictly coded and highly territorialized assemblages, such as schools and municipalities, while maintaining their autonomy.

Future research could explore similar community led CWS assemblages in other contexts, including outside of Europe, to see what we can learn and how their transformative potential can be institutionalized. Furthermore, both cases were mainly led by an individual, who had a significant impact on the overall assemblage, regarding the resources they put into it and their decision making. Their power seems to have a (dis)empowering (Avelino *et al.*, 2019) impact on the overall assemblage, as despite their energy and intensity increasing its affects, it could sometimes be overwhelming for other participants, causing one staff member in the Greek case to leave. Thus, future research could focus on more rhizomatic forms of SI initiatives, with less control of one individual, and how it differs to these SI assemblages.

Ethics and consent

Consent

Interview Participants were given an information sheet about the study and were required to sign a consent form prior to being interviewed. An ethical approval committee at Panteion University approved the study (Protocol Number: 44/ 30-9-2022). An example of the information sheet and consent form can be found above in the 'extended data' section.

Regarding participatory observation, the researcher made his identity as a researcher known to the users of the CWS by contacting the CWS in advance via email, requesting that they inform relevant stakeholders that there will be a researcher present for the given time period, and to notify them should they not consent to participate in the study to contact the researcher through contact details provided. When present on site, the researcher made his identity as a researcher known to the those participating in the CWS' activities, and verbal consent was required because of the short time duration of their visits. Moreover, although minors took part in some workshops (as stated in section 5.1.), the participants in the workshops were not interviewed or subjects of participant observation, and therefore it did not require consent.

Data availability

Due to ethical restrictions on data sharing should any reader or reviewer request data to be made available, small sections of de-identified quotes may be available on request by emailing the corresponding author. (colmstockdale@panteion.gr)

Extended data

Figshare: Colm_Stockdale_Information_Consent_Form. Stockdale, Colm (2024a). Colm_Stockdale_Information_Consent_Form.docx. figshare. Online resource. <https://doi.org/10.6084/m9.figshare.26356546.v1> *This project contains the following underlying data:*

The information sheet and consent form I used for my study to inform participants about the study and obtain their consent for participation.

Data is available under the terms of the Creative Commons Attribution 4.0 International license (CC-BY 4.0) (<https://creativecommons.org/licenses/by/4.0/>).

Figshare: Table 1 Regional Demographics, Stockdale, Colm (2024b). Table 1 Regional Demographics. figshare. Dataset. <https://doi.org/10.6084/m9.figshare.26356738.v1>

This project contains the following underlying data:

A table comparing regional demographics between the region of Western Greece and Upper Austria under indicators such as Population, GDP per Capita at current prices, Employment rate %, and % of persons at risk of poverty or social exclusion.

Data is available under the terms of the Creative Commons Attribution 4.0 International license (CC-BY 4.0) (<https://creativecommons.org/licenses/by/4.0/>).

Figshare: Interview Protocol. Stockdale, Colm (2024c). Interview Protocol. figshare. Online resource. <https://doi.org/10.6084/m9.figshare.26370316.v1>

This project contains the following underlying data:

The document contains the interview protocol for the study. This includes the research question and sample interview questions asked to interview participants.

Data is available under the terms of the Creative Commons Attribution 4.0 International license (CC-BY 4.0) (<https://creativecommons.org/licenses/by/4.0/>).

Figshare: Research Protocol. Stockdale, Colm (2024d). Research Protocol. figshare. Online resource. <https://doi.org/10.6084/m9.figshare.26370331.v1>

This project contains the following underlying data:

This document contains the research protocol used in the study. It contains the timeline for fieldwork and the Data collection procedures (data protection, identification of data sources).

Data is available under the terms of the Creative Commons Attribution 4.0 International license (CC-BY 4.0) (<https://creativecommons.org/licenses/by/4.0/>).

References

- Arampatzis A: **Social Innovation and austerity governance in Athens and Madrid: rethinking the changing contours of policy and practice.** *Eur Urban Reg Stud.* 2022; **29**(1): 45–58.
[Publisher Full Text](#)
- Arvidsson A: **Capitalism and the commons.** *Theor Cult Soc.* 2020; **37**(2): 3–30.
[Publisher Full Text](#)
- Avdikos V, Iliopoulou E: **Community-led coworking spaces: from co-location to collaboration and collectivization.** *Creative hubs in question: place, space and work in the creative economy.* 2019; 111–129.
[Publisher Full Text](#)
- Avdikos V, Merkel J: **Supporting open, shared and collaborative workspaces and hubs: recent transformations and policy implications.** *Urban Res Pract.* 2020; **13**(3): 348–357.
[Publisher Full Text](#)
- Avdikos V, Pettas D: **The new topologies of collaborative workspace assemblages between the market and the commons.** *Geoforum.* 2021; **121**: 44–52.
[Publisher Full Text](#)
- Avelino F, Wittmayer JM, Pel B, et al.: **Transformative Social Innovation and (dis)empowerment.** *Technol Forecast Soc Change.* 2019; **145**: 195–206.
[Publisher Full Text](#)
- Ayob N, Teasdale S, Fagan K: **How Social Innovation “came to be”: tracing the evolution of a contested concept.** *J Soc Policy.* 2016; **45**(4): 635–653.
[Publisher Full Text](#)
- Bandinelli C, Arvidsson A: **Brand yourself a changemaker!** *J Macromarketing.* 2013; **33**(1): 67–71.
[Publisher Full Text](#)
- Bartels K: **The double bind of Social Innovation: relational dynamics of change and resistance in neighbourhood governance.** *Urban Stud.* 2017; **54**(16): 3789–3805.
[Publisher Full Text](#)
- Bock BB: **Social innovation and sustainability; how to disentangle the buzzword and its application in the field of agriculture and rural development.** *Stud Agric Econ.* 2012; **114**(2): 57–63.
[Publisher Full Text](#)
- Bock BB: **Rural marginalisation and the role of social innovation; a turn towards nexogenous development and rural reconnection.** *Sociologia ruralis.* 2016; **56**(4): 552–573.
[Publisher Full Text](#)
- Bragaglia F: **Social Innovation as a “magic concept” for policy-makers and its implications for urban governance.** *Plan Theor.* 2021; **20**(2): 102–120.
[Publisher Full Text](#)
- Brooke R, Openshaw G, Farrow L, et al.: **Supporting places of work: incubators, accelerators, coworking spaces.** Greater London Authority, 2014.
[Reference Source](#)
- Brown J: **Curating the “Third Place”? Coworking and the mediation of creativity.** *Geoforum.* 2017; **82**(1): 112–126.
[Publisher Full Text](#)
- Bryman A: **Social research methods.** OUP Oxford, 2012.
[Reference Source](#)
- Buchanan I: **The problem of the body in Deleuze and Guattari, or, what can a body do?** *Body Soc.* 1997; **3**(3): 73–91.
[Publisher Full Text](#)
- Bureau of European Policy Advisers (BEPA): **Social Innovation: a decade of changes.** Luxembourg: Publications Office of the European Union, 2014.
[Reference Source](#)
- Chatterton P: **Building transitions to post-capitalist urban commons.** *TI Brit Geogr.* 2016; **41**(4): 403–415.
[Publisher Full Text](#)
- Chatterton P, Pusey A: **Beyond capitalist enclosure, commodification and alienation: postcapitalist praxis as commons, social production and useful doing.** *Prog Hum Geog.* 2020; **44**(1): 27–48.
[Publisher Full Text](#)
- Chen HC, Knierim A, Bock BB: **The emergence of Social Innovation in rural revitalisation practices: a comparative case study from Taiwan.** *J Rural Stud.* 2022; **90**(2): 134–146.
[Publisher Full Text](#)
- de Peuter G, Cohen NS, Saraco F: **The ambivalence of coworking: on the politics of an emerging work practice.** *Eur J Cult Stud* 2017; **20**(6): 687–706.
[Publisher Full Text](#)
- DeLanda M: **A new philosophy of society.** Bloomsbury, 2006.
[Reference Source](#)
- Deleuze G, Guattari F: **A thousand plateaus: capitalism and schizophrenia.** Bloomsbury Publishing, London, 1980.
[Reference Source](#)
- Dias R, Smith A: **Making in Brazil: can we make it work for social inclusion?** *Journal of Peer Production.* [Preprint], 2018; (12). (Accessed: 24 January 2022).
[Reference Source](#)
- Edensor T: **Performing rurality.** *Handbook of rural studies.* 2006; 484–495.
[Reference Source](#)
- Escobar A: **Reframing civilization(s): from critique to transitions.** *Globalizations.* 2021; 1–18.
[Publisher Full Text](#)
- Fougère M, Segercrantz B, Seeck H: **A critical reading of the European Union's Social Innovation policy discourse: (Re)legitimizing neoliberalism.** *Organization.* 2017; **24**(6): 819–843.
[Publisher Full Text](#)
- Gabriel N, Sarmiento E: **On power and the uses of genealogy for building community economies.** In: *The Handbook of Diverse Economies.* Edward Elgar Publishing, 2020; 411–418.
[Publisher Full Text](#)
- Gandini A, Cossu A: **The third wave of coworking: ‘Neo-corporate’ model versus ‘resilient’ practice.** *Eur J Cult Stud.* 2021; **24**(2): 430–447.
[Publisher Full Text](#)
- García M, Eizaguirre S, Pradel M: **Social Innovation and creativity in cities: a socially inclusive governance approach in two peripheral spaces of barcelona.** *City, Culture and Society.* 2015; **6**(4): 93–100.
[Publisher Full Text](#)
- Geels FW: **From sectoral systems of innovation to socio-technical systems: insights about dynamics and change from sociology and institutional theory.** *Res policy.* 2004; **33**(6–7): 897–920.
[Publisher Full Text](#)
- Gibson-Graham JK: **Diverse economies: performative practices for ‘other worlds’.** *Prog hum geog.* 2008; **32**(5): 613–632.
[Publisher Full Text](#)
- Gibson-Graham JK, Cameron J, Dombroski K, et al.: **Cultivating community economies: tools for building a livable world.** In: *The New Systems Reader.* Routledge, 2020; 410–432.
[Publisher Full Text](#)
- Gibson-Graham JK, Roelvink G: **‘Social innovation for community economies’.** In: *Social Innovation And Territorial Development.* Ashgate Publishing, 2009; 25–39.
[Reference Source](#)
- Gillard R, Gouldson A, Paavola J, et al.: **Transformational responses to climate change: beyond a systems perspective of social change in mitigation and adaptation.** *Wiley Interdisciplinary Reviews: Climate Change.* 2016; **7**(2): 251–265.
[Publisher Full Text](#)
- Godin B: **Social innovation: utopias of innovation from c. 1830 to the present.** In: *Social Innovation: The Intellectual History of Innovation Working Paper.* 2012; **11**: 1–5.
- Görmar F: **Collaborative workspaces in small towns and rural areas. The COVID-19 crisis as driver of new work models and an opportunity for sustainable regional development.** Working paper. 2021.
[Reference Source](#)
- Hardt M: **Affective Labor.** *Boundary 2.* 1999; **26**(2): 89–100.
[Reference Source](#)
- Haxeltine A, Avelino F, Pel B, et al.: **A framework for transformative social innovation (TRANSIT Working Paper # 5).** 2016.
[Publisher Full Text](#)
- Howaldt J, Butzin A, Domanski D, et al.: **Theoretical approaches to social innovation - a critical literature review. A deliverable of the project: “Social Innovation: Driving Force of Social Change” (SI-DRIVE).** Dortmund: Sozialforschungsstelle, 2014; (Accessed: 30 May 2022).
[Publisher Full Text](#)
- Jessop B, Moulaert F, Hulgård L, et al.: **Social innovation research: a new stage in innovation analysis.** *The International Handbook On Social Innovation: Collective Action, Social Learning And Transdisciplinary Research.* 2013; 110–130.
- JRC: **My Place.** 2024; Accessed 30 April 2024.
[Reference Source](#)
- Klinenberg E: **Palaces for the people. how social infrastructure can help fight inequality, polarization, and the decline of civic life.** Crown, 2018.
[Reference Source](#)
- Law J: **After method: mess in social science research.** Routledge, 2004.
[Reference Source](#)
- Marmo L, Avdikos V: **The regional geography of collaborative workspaces in Europe, MSCA CORAL-ITN Brief 1, Athens.** 2024.
[Reference Source](#)
- Marques P, Morgan K, Richardson R: **Social innovation in question: the theoretical and practical implications of a contested concept.** *Environment and Planning C: Politics and Space.* 2018; **36**(3): 496–512.
[Publisher Full Text](#)
- Martinelli F: **Historical roots of social change: philosophies and movements.** In: *Can Neighbourhoods Save the City?* Routledge, 2010; 33–64.
[Reference Source](#)
- Merkel J: **Coworking spaces as social infrastructures of care.** In: Merkel J, Pettas, D., Avdikos, V. (Eds.), *Coworking Spaces.* Springer, Cham, 2023; 83–95.
[Publisher Full Text](#)

Miller E: **Reimagining livelihoods: life beyond economy, society, and environment.** University of Minnesota Press, 2019.
[Publisher Full Text](#)

Moulaert F, MacCallum D: **Advanced introduction to Social Innovation.** Edward Elgar Publishing, 2019.
[Reference Source](#)

Moulaert F, MacCallum D, Mehmood A, *et al.*: **The international handbook on social innovation: collective action, social learning and transdisciplinary research.** 2013.
[Reference Source](#)

Moulaert F, Martinelli F, Swyngedouw E, *et al.*: **Towards alternative model(s) of local innovation.** *Urban Stud.* 2005; **42**(11): 1969–1990.
[Publisher Full Text](#)

Moulaert F, Mehmood A: **Towards a Social Innovation (SI) based epistemology in local development analysis: lessons from twenty years of EU research.** *Eur Plan Stud.* 2020; **28**(3): 434–453.
[Publisher Full Text](#)

Moulaert F, Mehmood A, MacCallum D, *et al.*: **Social innovation as a trigger for transformations-the role of research.** Publications Office of the European Union, 2017.
[Reference Source](#)

Moulaert F, Swyngedouw E, Martinelli F, *et al.*: **Can neighbourhoods save the city?: community development and social innovation.** Routledge, 2010.
[Publisher Full Text](#)

Mulgan G: **The process of Social Innovation. Innovations: Technology, Governance, Globalization.** 2006; **1**(2): 145–162.
[Publisher Full Text](#)

Murray R, Caulier-Grice J, Mulgan G: **The open book of Social Innovation.** London: Nesta, 2010; **24**.
[Reference Source](#)

Pel B, Haxeltine A, Avelino F, *et al.*: **Towards a theory of transformative Social Innovation: a relational framework and 12 propositions.** *Res Policy.* 2020; **49**(8): 104080.
[Publisher Full Text](#)

Richter R, Christmann GB: **On the role of key players in rural Social Innovation processes.** *J Rural Stud.* 2023; **99**: 213–222.
[Publisher Full Text](#)

Rosa H: **Resonance: a sociology of our relationship to the world.** John Wiley & Sons, 2019.
[Reference Source](#)

Schmidt S, Brinks V: **Open creative labs: spatial settings at the intersection of communities and organizations.** *Creat Innov Manag.* 2017; **26**(3): 291–299.
[Publisher Full Text](#)

Scott-Cato M, Hillier J: **How could we study climate-related Social Innovation? Applying Deleuzian philosophy to Transition Towns.** *Environ*

Polit. 2010; **19**(6): 869–887.

[Publisher Full Text](#)

Slaby J, Mühlhoff R: **Affect.** In: *Affective Societies.* Routledge, 2019; 27–42.

Smith TS: **Stand back and watch us': Post-capitalist practices in the maker movement.** *Environ Plan A Economy Space.* 2020; **52**(3): 593–610.
[Publisher Full Text](#)

Smith A, Raven R: **What is protective space? reconsidering niches in transitions to sustainability.** *Res Policy.* 2012; **41**(6): 1025–1036.
[Publisher Full Text](#)

Stockdale C: **Colm Stockdale Information Consent Form.docx.** figshare. Online resource, 2024a.

<http://www.doi.org/10.6084/m9.figshare.26356546.v1>

Stockdale C: **Table 1 Regional Demographics.** figshare. Dataset. 2024b.

<http://www.doi.org/10.6084/m9.figshare.26356738.v1>

Stockdale C: **Interview Protocol.** figshare. Online resource, 2024c.

<http://www.doi.org/10.6084/m9.figshare.26370316.v1>

Stockdale C: **Research Protocol.** figshare. Online resource, 2024d.

<http://www.doi.org/10.6084/m9.figshare.26370331.v1>

Swyngedouw E: **Governance innovation and the Citizen: the Janus face of governance-beyond-the-State.** *Urban Stud.* 2005; **42**(11): 1991–2006.
[Publisher Full Text](#)

Tomaz E, Moriset B, Teller J: **Rural coworking spaces in the COVID-19 era: a window of opportunity?** In: *The COVID-19 Pandemic and The Future of Working Spaces.* Routledge, 2022; 122–135.
[Reference Source](#)

Törnberg A: **Prefigurative politics and social change: a typology drawing on transition studies.** *Distinktion: Journal of Social Theory.* 2021; **22**(1): 83–107.
[Publisher Full Text](#)

Van der Have RP, Rubalcaba L: **Social innovation research: an emerging area of innovation studies?** *Res Policy.* 2016; **45**(9): 1923–1935.
[Publisher Full Text](#)

Vidailliet B, Bousalham Y: **Coworking spaces as places where economic diversity can be articulated: towards a theory of syntopia.** *Organization.* 2020; **27**(1): 60–87.
[Publisher Full Text](#)

[Publisher Full Text](#)

Willett J: **Affective assemblages and local economies.** Rowman & Littlefield, 2021.
[Reference Source](#)

Wright EO: **Envisioning real utopias.** London; New York: Verso, 2010.

[Reference Source](#)

Yin RK: **Case study research and applications.** 6th edn. SAGE Publications US, 2018; (Accessed: 10 January 2023).
[Reference Source](#)

[Reference Source](#)

Zink V: **Affective communities.** In: *Affective Societies.* Routledge, 2019; 289–299.
[Reference Source](#)

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Current Peer Review Status: ? ? ? ?

Version 1

Reviewer Report 25 October 2024

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Ignasi Capdevila

Paris School of Business, Paris, France

Introduction and Framing of the Research Question

The article would benefit from a stronger framing of its research purpose and contributions within the introduction. Specifically, the authors should clearly articulate the research question early on to orient the reader toward the study's specific aims and relevance. A more explicit statement of the research gap would enhance understanding of why this study's focus on rural collaborative workspaces (CWS) and social innovation (SI) is both timely and necessary. To further contextualize this, the introduction could summarize existing assumptions within SI and CWS research, setting the stage for why these topics merit investigation together and framing CWS as potential vehicles for community empowerment in rural economies. A sharper outline of these elements will help readers recognize the paper's unique position within the literature and its potential contributions to SI and rural economy discourse.

Literature Review

The literature review would benefit from a more cohesive structure that clarifies the logical progression between sections. As it stands, there are limited transitions, which can make it difficult for readers to follow the development of the argument. To enhance readability, the review could begin by briefly covering the foundational literature on SI, followed by an exploration of CWS-specific studies, before focusing on the intersection of SI and CWS as a distinct research area. This organization would help clarify the gap the authors are addressing and lead naturally into the statement of the research question. Additionally, the analytical framework of assemblage theory could then be introduced as a means to address this question, explaining how the chosen theoretical perspective provides a lens through which to interpret the transformative potential of rural CWS. This restructuring would improve the paper's clarity and better situate the study within existing scholarship.

Methodology

While the authors employ a qualitative comparative case study design, further detail regarding the data collection and analysis would enhance the methodology section. For example, more in-depth descriptions of data coding, the interview protocol, and any analytical software or techniques used would strengthen the study's rigor and replicability. Moreover, the section discussing the localities is somewhat general and does not provide enough specific context to deepen understanding of how these distinct settings might shape or limit the CWS' potential impact. Since the paper aims to offer a comparative analysis, a justification for selecting Greece and Austria as cases is crucial. Expanding on why these two cases were chosen and how their specific socio-economic conditions relate to the research question would provide readers with a stronger foundation for interpreting the findings.

Results and Discussion

To improve clarity, the authors should more explicitly delineate the results and discussion sections. In its current form, there is some blending between the two, with references to the literature appearing in the results section and data quotes embedded within the discussion. This crossover risks confusing readers about where empirical observations end and theoretical interpretation begins. To address this, the authors could clarify the data structure in the results, using clear subheadings and more direct data quotes to support their findings. For example, using a "show, don't tell" approach would enhance transparency, allowing readers to directly see the data backing each claim and strengthening the study's credibility. In the discussion, removing direct data quotes and instead focusing on theoretical analysis and implications would reinforce the interpretive flow, making it easier for readers to understand the study's contribution to broader SI and community economy literature.

The discussion section could be strengthened by reinforcing key concepts introduced in the literature review. Some theoretical terms, such as Diverse and Community Economies (DCE), are used in the discussion without being sufficiently elaborated upon in the earlier review, creating a disconnect between sections. A brief but clear presentation of these concepts in the literature review would provide readers with a stronger grounding and allow the discussion to delve into these frameworks more seamlessly. Additionally, referencing back to the research question and explicitly connecting findings to the theoretical concepts of assemblage and community economies would improve coherence and underscore the study's contributions to these fields.

The methodology presents the two case studies as contrasting examples; however, the results section does not fully explore how these cases respond differently (or similarly) to the research question. A more focused comparative analysis would clarify whether the observed differences in CWS functionality or outcomes are due to local cultural and economic factors, or if they share common transformative elements despite contextual variations. Bringing these contrasts to the forefront would enrich the study's insights into how CWS may function under varying conditions and provide a more comprehensive understanding of their potential across diverse rural settings.

In sum, the paper offers valuable insights into the transformative potential of rural CWS through a theoretically informed case study approach. However, the paper would benefit from improvements in structuring the literature review, clarifying the methodology, separating results from discussion, reinforcing theoretical concepts in line with the discussion, and enhancing readability. These refinements would strengthen the paper's academic rigor and readability,

reinforcing its contribution to the discourse on SI, CWS, and post-capitalist community economies.

Minor comments:

- Correct typographical errors, e.g., "Western greece" should be "Western Greece" (p.6).
- Avoid acronyms in titles (e.g., replace "CWS" with the full term "Collaborative Workspaces").
- Define any acronyms when first introduced, and avoid overuse to enhance readability. Specifically: Clarify "MBL" on p.8, "DCE" on p.12, and "CE" on p.13.
- Eliminate redundant phrasing: "For example, For example" (p.10)

Is the work clearly and accurately presented and does it engage with the current literature?

Partly

Is the study design appropriate and is the work technically sound?

Yes

Are sufficient details of methods and analysis provided to allow replication by others?

Partly

Are all the source data and materials underlying the results available?

Yes

If applicable, is the statistical analysis and its interpretation appropriate?

Not applicable

Are the conclusions drawn adequately supported by the results?

Partly

Competing Interests: No competing interests were disclosed.

Reviewer Expertise: Qualitative methods

I confirm that I have read this submission and believe that I have an appropriate level of expertise to confirm that it is of an acceptable scientific standard, however I have significant reservations, as outlined above.

Author Response 19 Dec 2024

Colm Stockdale

Thank you for your insightful comments. The introduction has been reworked accordingly to articulate the research purpose. The organization of the text has been re-worked to accommodate this. With a separate literature review (Section 2) and conceptual framework (Section 3). The methodology section has been updated to reflect this comment, regarding data coding, the interview protocol, and the analytical software used. Moreover, a section has been added that has more in-depth information regarding the contexts and how they relate to the research question. The results section has been amended accordingly. There are several new quotes in the results section, and subheadings have been fixed. Quotes

have been removed from the discussion section, which has also been amended to allow for more reflection on the research questions and the contribution of the study. Moreover, the concepts are presented more clearly in the literature review and conceptual framework sections. The discussion section also now reflects the comments regarding the different contexts. The minor comments have also been addressed.

Competing Interests: No competing interests were disclosed.

Reviewer Report 21 October 2024

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Athina Arampatzi

Spatial Planning and Development, Aristotle University of Thessaloniki, Thessaloniki, Greece

Dear authors,

The manuscript deals in a very engaged way with the timely topic of the ongoing and fast development of collaborative work spaces (CWS), by exploring two cases of rural CWS in Greece and Austria. Through an engagement with diverse concepts and literature, it seeks to elicit the transformative potential of CWS for local communities and, by extension, their impact on social change more broadly.

The manuscript is clearly presented in terms of its goals, aimed contribution to the literature and the analysis of its empirical material. The research design described is appropriate and the work carried out is sound, in terms of both fieldwork and analysis of research data. The methodological approach is also sound, while the necessary information on source data and results are available to the readers. Finally, the conclusions make an interesting attempt to bring forward the key arguments raised and outline relevant limitations and future research pathways.

Having said these, the manuscript, while overall comprehensive, could benefit from a clearer and more precise delineation of its conceptual framework, to facilitate even further the development of the analysis and the conclusions sections, and stress its original contribution to the field of study.

Here are some suggestions that could work towards these directions:

1. The work carried out holds, I believe, strong originality in terms of discussing CWS and SI in rural contexts, as opposed to most literature focusing on urban ones. This needs to be stressed throughout and comparative lines need be drawn and fleshed out in the discussion and conclusions sections (as well discussed in the comparative lens used between two

- different contexts of southern and northern Europe). For example, what differences there exist in terms of transformative potential of CWS in rural vs urban contexts based on the research? Are there specific lessons to be learned from this comparison?
2. There is a plethora of concepts employed, which, eventually, in my opinion, blur the core arguments to be delivered, and this is also reflected on the manuscript's title. While each one has its own merit, taken all together might not work in favor of the manuscript's goals. If, for instance, the core question posed is "how do local assemblages of CWS contribute alternative forms of community economies and/or transformative forms of social innovation beyond mainstream local development" the conceptual framework to be chosen towards this end might need to be more focused and specifically deal with this (or others) question as a guiding direction of the manuscript. Here another issue pops up: could assemblage thinking work better on a more methodological level to trace all the qualities, capacities, actors, networks, their relations, desires, affects, cultural trajectories etc. of such local community formations?
 3. Discussion: I am a bit unsure whether Wright's approach works here to unpack, compare and expand on the manuscript's main contribution, which, again, I believe lies on the rural vs urban comparison.
 4. Conclusions: the authors might want to highlight and expand on the main contribution of the manuscript, e.g. what does the shift from individual to collective empowerment observed in rural areas contribute to mainstream literature on urban contexts? Can we rethink the idea of transformative SI in this regard? If an institutionalization of informal activity is deemed necessary for CWS to develop in rural areas, what would this mean in relation to cities? And also, maybe expand on the limitations of gatekeepers/hierarchical positions within local assemblages, and their horizontal rhizomatic character.

Hopefully the above suggestions provide some useful directions to ameliorate the manuscript and strengthen its core arguments.

Thank you for sharing your very interesting work

Kind regards,
Athina Arampatzi

Is the work clearly and accurately presented and does it engage with the current literature?

Partly

Is the study design appropriate and is the work technically sound?

Yes

Are sufficient details of methods and analysis provided to allow replication by others?

Yes

Are all the source data and materials underlying the results available?

Yes

If applicable, is the statistical analysis and its interpretation appropriate?

Not applicable

Are the conclusions drawn adequately supported by the results?

Partly

Competing Interests: No competing interests were disclosed.**Reviewer Expertise:** urban studies, urban geography, social innovation, urban governance, social solidarity economy, urban commons, social movements**I confirm that I have read this submission and believe that I have an appropriate level of expertise to confirm that it is of an acceptable scientific standard, however I have significant reservations, as outlined above.**

Author Response 19 Dec 2024

Colm Stockdale

Thank you for the interesting comments.

1. The urban-rural comparisons have been incorporated in the conclusion, but not in the discussion, which does reflect the differences between northern and southern Europe. The research was conducted in a rural context and there was no intention, and subsequently, no data was gathered on the urban level. As such an urban-rural comparison cannot be made. However, we have reflected on what a rural-urban comparison might mean for future research in the conclusion section.
2. The manuscript's main goal is to provide a novel theoretical framework to reconceptualize SI processes and their transformative potential, which is examined through CWS. Therefore, the main conceptual and analytical concepts are assemblage thinking and post-capitalist thinking (Diverse and Community Economies and Wright's framework). While the suggested amendment would allow a possibly clearer explanation, the combination of both assemblage thinking and post-capitalist thinking are required to enable a re-conceptualization of SI processes and their transformative processes. The text has been re-worked to now include a section (section 3) for the conceptual framework, for it to be clearer for the reader. Moreover, the methodology section has been reworked to include assemblage thinking also as a methodological device.
3. The main contribution of the manuscript is to provide a theoretical framework that re-conceptualizes SI processes and allows us to understand their transformative potential. Moreover, the first reviewer commented "using the Wright types of utopian change as steps toward a new society is promising." We have used Wright's tripartite distinction of ruptural/symbiotic/ interstitial transformation to support our arguments and in particular, to unpack the different transformative practices (and strategies) a CWS might have inside and outside of the organisation. We also believe that this adds on the DCE framework and can provide a new understanding of the different community economies and their symbiotic or interstitial practices with/against the market and the state.
4. Thank you for the insightful comment. This has been worked in to the main text in the

conclusion, regarding the contribution of the framework other than the framework itself. Particularly the last paragraphs brings in some of these reflections, for example how we may re-consider rural and urban when it comes to transformations. The limitations of gatekeepers, and the rhizomatic character of the CWS assemblages has also been expanded upon in the beginning of the discussion.

Competing Interests: No competing interests were disclosed.

Reviewer Report 17 October 2024

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Gary Bosworth

Northumbria University, Newcastle upon Tyne, England, UK

This is a very interesting paper investigating the social innovation that is emerging within the CWS sector. The attempt to apply Assemblages and Diverse and Community Economies theories is quite ambitious and I would like to see a clearer aim and set of conclusions that identify either: (i) how these theories help to generate new understanding about CWS or (ii) how the research advances these theories by this new application.

Moving to a few more specific points, the final paragraph of the introduction could benefit from a slightly clearer aim and/or justification of why you landed on social innovation here. The definition is clear, but is coworking really SI? Presumably there is at least some aspect of commercial innovation going on here if the venues are to be economically viable. Fundamentally, coworking is a service that people consume for personal benefit so I think we need to be careful when discussing the social innovation aspects of CWS.

I like the details of the case study areas – although note the need for a capital G on Greece in the subheading. I would like just a little more detail on the methods though – perhaps a table summarizing the characteristics of the 30 interviewees and I am also curious how you achieved 3,000 hours of participant observation by spending 1 month in each location?!

I am interested that you say the CWS “acts as a place where different people who would not normally cross paths can meet” – I have often wondered just how much mixing occurs in these places. It would be good if you could elaborate – I see the multiple user groups, but do they really mix? And then, in terms of Social Innovation, you can start digging more deeply into the reconfiguration of networks. I also like that part of the rationale for participating is to collectively address weak infrastructure etc so, although I would still argue that is an example of transactional consumption, it is at least more cooperative in the way that it requires a critical mass of users to bring about any impact. This first section of the findings has only one quotation from the primary research, so perhaps adding a few more would be helpful.

The final conclusions, although supported by the research, just feel a little underwhelming. This

appears to be the main claim:

“The findings reveal that CWS play a significant role in addressing social needs and facilitating grassroots SI practices, creating affective relations that contribute to the transformation of individual to collective subjectivities. CWS seem to provide a site where the unmet needs of the local people are negotiated, redefined and are covered in a co-creative and collective manner. This is happening in a DCE framework, where affective labour mostly performs.”

It would help the reader to see a clearer re-interpretation of the earlier theories or a summary of how those theories have deepened our understanding of CWS in order to address the initial aims of the paper. Perhaps it would help to state the more applied and more theoretical conclusions separately before a final paragraph that focuses back in on the SI processes that are developing within CWS and their wider communities?

A final very specific point, on P1 regarding this quotation: “Recent research suggests that 66% of CWS are located in urban regions, while the rest (34%) are in intermediate or rural regions” For this statement, it would probably be worth noting that it is difficult to collate accurate data for more rural areas given the variety of spaces that might class as CWS. Also, you should state the geography to which the comment relate – is that Europe?

Essentially, in addition to the minor typographical, methodological and explanation details, I would just like to see a few lines in the conclusion that speak back to a clearer aim which would help to frame the paper and make it easier for the reader to navigate the complexity of Assemblages, Social Innovation and Diverse and Community Economies.

Is the work clearly and accurately presented and does it engage with the current literature?

Yes

Is the study design appropriate and is the work technically sound?

Yes

Are sufficient details of methods and analysis provided to allow replication by others?

Partly

Are all the source data and materials underlying the results available?

Partly

If applicable, is the statistical analysis and its interpretation appropriate?

Not applicable

Are the conclusions drawn adequately supported by the results?

Yes

Competing Interests: No competing interests were disclosed.

I confirm that I have read this submission and believe that I have an appropriate level of expertise to confirm that it is of an acceptable scientific standard, however I have significant reservations, as outlined above.

Author Response 19 Dec 2024

Colm Stockdale

Regarding the first comment, the introduction overall has been amended to incorporate this and comments from other reviewers. The first paragraphs introduce the polycrisis and the rationale behind the necessity for societal transformations, of which social innovation is one of many means of achieving this. Coworking is not SI, and the paper does not state so. The CWS engage in SI processes (among many other activities, such as commercial innovation). Moreover, this paper is not about coworking spaces, it is about collaborative workspaces that includes a diversity of organizational forms. Through the framework of diversity and community economies we acknowledge in the discussion there are aspects of commercial innovation occurring. This is particularly clear in the case of WGH rather than the municipally funded CUA, as the former needs to trade on the market and write funding applications to remain economically viable, commercial innovation occurs in actions such as their boat tours or their festival. However, this is not the focus of the paper, the focus being what is the potential of these practices for post-capitalist transformations? Moreover, through the analytical framework of assemblage thinking, we go beyond spatial conceptions of CWS as bounded entities, and view them as CWS assemblages, which is clear from the interactions and actions both CWS have with their local communities.

Regarding the methods, a table has been added to section 4.1, and the typo of 3,000 hours has been corrected to 300. Regarding the comment 'how much mixing occurs in these places' this has been further elaborated upon. Particularly in section 5.1.2. , comparing the two cases under how much key individuals take part in other areas and actions of the CWS. Additional quotes have been added to the first section of the findings. The final conclusion has been changed, which now offers a summary of the findings, followed by a short and clear explanation of how the theories have contributed to thinking about social innovation and collaborative workspaces. The CORAL-ITN survey and the methods used for obtaining the relevant data are now acknowledged in the text, as well as the limitations of that methodology (specific keywords etc). The third paragraph in the conclusion, now states the main aim and contribution of the paper, and how they enrich both CWS and SI theory.

Competing Interests: No competing interests were disclosed.

Reviewer Report 16 October 2024

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? **Bettina Bock**

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This paper discusses the results of a study that compares the functioning of two rural collaborative workspaces in Greece and Austria, particularly the insights gained through elaborating a novel theoretical framework created for this purpose. The work is well embedded in current literature on workspaces, social innovation in rural areas, as well as recent theories aiming to understand social innovation and the coming into existence of new community-oriented economies. The work is clearly and accurately presented. It includes relevant information on the study design, which is both appropriate and technically sound. The paper provides sufficient insight into the methods used and provides access to the data collected. This should allow for replication with the remark that qualitative analysis is notoriously difficult to replicate. The paper does not refer to any statistical analysis. The conclusions drawn are supported by the results. The paper is particularly interesting as it tests the insights that may be gained when departing from a novel theoretical perspective. It does present empiric results, but more engaging is the potential that the new theoretical frameworks offer for understanding collective workspaces and other socially innovative initiatives in what transformation they promote and what could be done to support their ability to do so. In my view, the attempt to go beyond usual social innovation studies in which we focus on the results achieved, this study allows us to better understand the innovative elements of the process of change while keeping track of the specific context in which the innovative workspaces operate. I was engaged by the interlinkages made with social innovation literature, community economy and utopian thinking as altogether, they allow us to tease out what is really innovative and transformative. Using assemblage theory helps us to understand how social innovation can be understood in context and in interaction with the 'outside world'. In building this new framework, they manage to reveal where the workspaces start to make a difference by changing social dynamics at the collective level as well as among individuals who start to think differently thereby considering themselves as parts of collectives. Also, using the Wright types of utopian change as steps toward a new society is promising. Overall, I think the paper is almost ready for indexing. As a reader, I would have liked to see a clear formulation of research questions, clarifying also that the main purpose is a theoretical one. The study is presented as a comparative one, and in the result sections, both cases are presented. There is also some reference to comparing, however, focusing mainly on the correspondences. Certainly, when arriving at the point of the transformative potential, it would be interesting to learn more about the differences between the cases. One could imagine that the transformative potential is higher in the case of Greece, given the more peripheral context and higher attractiveness of social economies/commons, but maybe the difference in potential is also related to differences between what the workspaces are and do. We can, after all, learn a lot about the novel theoretical framework where it identifies differences or where it fits better given the context.

Is the work clearly and accurately presented and does it engage with the current literature?

Yes

Is the study design appropriate and is the work technically sound?

Yes

Are sufficient details of methods and analysis provided to allow replication by others?

Yes

Are all the source data and materials underlying the results available?

Yes

If applicable, is the statistical analysis and its interpretation appropriate?

Not applicable

Are the conclusions drawn adequately supported by the results?

Yes

Competing Interests: No competing interests were disclosed.

Reviewer Expertise: rural development, social innovation, peripheralisation, community initiatives

I confirm that I have read this submission and believe that I have an appropriate level of expertise to confirm that it is of an acceptable scientific standard, however I have significant reservations, as outlined above.

Author Response 19 Dec 2024

Colm Stockdale

Thank you for the comments and feedback. The research questions are now stated at the end of section 2.2. at the end of the literature review.

Regarding the comparison of the cases and their transformative potential, it is a very constructive comment. This was integrated into the beginning of the discussion section.

Competing Interests: No competing interests were disclosed.
